

UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

There is no law in the Czech Republic that deals with gender-based violence or sexual harassment specifically in higher education institutions and research organisations. There are several national policies that mention sexual harassment, but all of them devote only a few sentences to the issue, usually in the form of recommendations for the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports to deal with this phenomenon.

The number of institutions that have taken concrete steps to deal with this issue has increased more substantially just very recently (especially in the past two years). These steps were prompted by instruments introduced to tackle this issue as part of various national and international research and higher education policies. An important factor was the introduction of financial support for higher education institutions (HEIs) by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports to motivate HEIs to set up their strategic management in accordance with the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for Recruitment and apply for the HR Excellence in Research award. Many Czech HEIs used this support, and it led many of them to initiate the first steps to promote gender equality (including introducing measures to prevent and eliminate gender-based violence).

Other developments at the national level also served as incentives for institutions to take action. “Dealing with sexual harassment” was included as a recommended activity in the 2019 Implementation Plan of the Ministry of Education’s Long-Term Plan for Educational and Scientific Activities, Research, Development and Innovation, and Artistic and Other Creative Activities in Higher Education 2016–2020. The financial scheme linked to this plan, the Centralised Development Programme, also offered support for activities that focus on promoting gender equality (including fighting sexual harassment). Universities are also regularly reminded of the need to take action in this area by a requirement imposed by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports to report annually on how they deal with sexual harassment (a requirement in place since 2018). In addition, in 2020 sexual harassment was for the first time included (as part of the gender equality indicator) in the Methodology for Evaluating Research Organisations and Research, Development and Innovation.

These instruments are applied primarily in the higher education sector. There are no similar stimuli for other Research Performing Organisations (RPOs). For this reason, the problem of gender-based violence has so far been addressed primarily in the university environment but less in terms of concrete institutional policies.

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

The University of Ostrava has two policy documents that address gender-based violence. Both of them are non-dedicated policies, that is, more broadly conceived documents that only make mention of gender-based violence:

- 1) Strategický záměr Ostravské univerzity 2021–2025/University of Ostrava Strategic Plan 2021–2025
- 2) Pracovní řád Ostravské univerzity/Employment Code of the University of Ostrava

In its Strategic Plan, the University of Ostrava sets the goal of appointing an ombudsperson to deal with sexual harassment (as well as several other problems). Another goal is to develop methodological support to prevent inappropriate behaviour, provide training, and raise awareness. The Strategic Plan touches on the problem of sexual harassment both at the staff-staff level and at the teacher-student level. At the staff-staff level, however, the Strategic Plan deals with acts of gender-based violence only implicitly. It is the university's management team that is responsible for the plan's implementation. The Implementation Plan for 2021 includes the objective of ensuring prevention, protection and provision of services. In accordance with the above-mentioned goals, the position of ombudsperson was created at the Faculty of Medicine (but not yet at the university level or at any other faculties).

The Employment Code of the University of Ostrava sets out the various obligations of employees and the sanctions resulting from non-compliance. Paragraph 3 lists and defines several types of conduct that are considered a major breach of duty. This includes the following: (e) 'harassment, which means undesirable behaviour that has the intention or effect of reducing a person's dignity and creating an intimidating, hostile, degrading, humiliating or offensive environment, or conduct that may legitimately be perceived as a condition for decisions affecting the exercise of rights and obligations arising from legal relationships'; and (f) 'sexual harassment, which means conduct under point (e) that is of a sexual nature'.

URLs

- › University of Ostrava Strategic Plan 2021–2025:
<https://dokumenty.osu.cz/rektorat/dz/szou-2021-2025-en.pdf>
- › Employment Code of the University of Ostrava:
https://dokumenty.osu.cz/osu/pracovni_rad_2019.pdf

Entry into force: The University of Ostrava Strategic Plan 2021–2025 entered into force in 2021, while the Employment Code of the University of Ostrava was approved in 2019.

TRAINING

The objective to provide training and raise awareness to deal with sexual harassment both at the teacher-student level and at the staff-staff level is included in the University of Ostrava Strategic Plan 2021–2025. Nothing further is specified in the document.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

Not specified.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: While the University of Ostrava Strategic Plan 2021–2025 only addresses the issue of sexual harassment, the Employment Code of the University of Ostrava also refers to gender harassment.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: The two policies combined address the following **6Ps**: prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, the provision of services and policy. The University of Ostrava Strategic Plan 2021–2025 addresses prevalence (but only at the staff-staff level), prevention (methodological support, training, and raising awareness), protection and the provision of services (establishing the position of an ombudsman). The Employment Code of the University of Ostrava specifies protection, prosecution and policy via its complaint procedure.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Intersectionality addressed

No

Specific vulnerable groups

Not defined

Target groups

The two policies address academic staff, non-academic staff, and students. No other target groups are identified.

Bystanders addressed: No.

Role of perpetrators addressed: No.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: Not specified.

Monitoring: No.

Evaluation: No.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

The Employment Code of the University of Ostrava specifies a procedure for dealing with GBV at the staff-staff level.

The policy defines: who to contact, how to report, the investigation process, responsible persons or units, outcomes and sanctions.

Who to contact: Complaints are to be lodged with a person in a superior position to the complainant and the alleged perpetrator (a person on the first level superior to both of them, serving as an investigator).

How to report: The complaint must contain a description of the act that the complainant sees as a breach of the alleged perpetrator's obligations. At the same time, the complainant shall provide a list of witnesses or other evidence that can substantiate their claim, such as a camera recording. Anonymous complaints will not be considered.

Description of the investigation: The investigator or his/her authorised representative will inform the alleged perpetrator of the complaint. S/he shall also write down statements of witnesses proposed by the complainant or secured by the complainant, or, where appropriate, collect evidence relevant to the complaint. The complaint may be assessed by an investigator as justified or unjustified. In both cases, the investigator will inform the complainant and the alleged perpetrator of the sanctions to be applied. Any complaint against the Rector of the university will be dealt with by its Ethics Committee.

Responsible persons, units: A person in a position superior to the complainant and alleged perpetrator (and in some specific cases also the Ethics Committee). The Ethics Committee also serves as the appellate body.

Outcomes: The complainant and the alleged perpetrator are informed about any sanctions that may follow. An unjustified complaint may be considered a breach of the obligations in the sense of creating an intimidating, hostile, degrading, humiliating or offensive environment.

Sanctions: Sexual harassment and harassment are classified as major breaches of duty, which may lead to an immediate termination of employment. Depending on the assessment of the intensity of a specific breach of duty, the employer may respond with a call for disciplinary action, termination of employment following a notice of reproach, or immediate termination of employment.

Additional information

In addition to the above-mentioned documents, the university also has a Code of Ethics for Employees and Students of the University of Ostrava (approved in 2018), which may also be applied in cases of gender-based violence. The document does not name different forms of gender-based violence explicitly. Nevertheless, it states as rules of ethical conduct that employees and students must 'respect the basic rules of interpersonal relations and decent behaviour' and that teachers must not engage in or cause 'personal humiliation, immoral behaviour, or coercion' and must not 'abuse their position in relation to students'.

Moreover, in April 2022, the University published its Action Plan for Gender Equality of the University of Ostrava for the years 2022–2025. This document further elaborates on strategic priorities formulated in the University of Ostrava Strategic Plan 2021–2025. It introduces four main measures related to gender-based violence, each of them targeting both employees and students (p. 5): 1) launching a survey mapping gender-based violence at the University, 2) creating an internal regulation establishing rules for the area of social safety, 3) developing a communication platform enabling open and safe communication of issues falling under this area to solve problems in their early stages, 4) establishing the position of a university ombudsperson. The Plan also mentions the aim to raise awareness among staff and students.

URL: <https://dokumenty.osu.cz/osu/akcni-plan-genderove-rovnosti-ou-2022-2025.pdf>

URL: <https://dokumenty.osu.cz/osu/eticky-kodex-en-30082018.pdf>

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Jana Dvořáčková in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

